

CMC DAMAGE PREDICTION BY MICRO-MACRO MODELING

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SUMMARY: The non-linear stress-strain curve obtains under tensile loading, is related to a multi-scale development of damage phenomena like matrix microcracking, fibre or bundle debonding and fibre breakage. To describe this damage evolution and its consequences on the industrial components mechanical behaviour, correlation between the different scales and reliable homogenization procedure have been studied. This micro-macro model is applied to various SiC-SiC (CVI) and a C-SiC (CVI) made by S.E.P (Société Européenne de Propulsion, France).

KEYWORDS: CMC, micro-macro, damage mechanics, SiC-SiC, C-SiC.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic matrix composites have reached a critical stage in their development and application partly because of a lack of specific design procedure and life prediction methodologies. The development of reliable models for describing the thermomechanical behaviour of such laminates composite is necessary. In this study, we propose a micro-mechanical model able to simulate the evolution of damage for various CMC under complex thermomechanical loading up to failure. For ceramic matrix composites, several damage mechanisms could occur: matrix microcracking, fiber/matrix debonding, and fiber breakage. These mechanisms are strongly anisotropic: cracks could be perpendicular to the loading direction or partly deviated by the reinforcement orientation. Furthermore, these cracks could be opened or closed depending on the loading and on the thermal residual stresses induced by cure processing. These aspects are introduced in the proposal model.

The tool being used is the anisotropic damage theory, developed by Ladeveze (1983[1], 1995[2]). It has already been applied to various composites as laminate carbon/epoxy (Ladeveze, Le Dantec, 1992[3]) or woven ceramic composites (Aubart, 1992[4]; Ladeveze, Gasser, Allix, 1994[5]). One of the difficulties of this approach is to outline the main phenomena from the experimental response and then to build the damage laws at the appropriate scale. Since the damage phenomena occur at microscopic scale, it seems appropriate to study damage at this micro-scale. Moreover, this scale enhances the role of interphases between fiber and matrix and takes into account the thermal residual stresses effect. Thermal residual stresses could not be neglected for many composites like C-SiC, while it leads to inelastic strains. The evolution of the constituent's damage (fiber, matrix, interface) on the local state stress can be computed. Homogenization plays a prominent role. A description of the calculation procedure, detailed in Engrand & al. (1993)[6], is briefly described here. We focus this paper on the damage kinematics introduced at the micro-scale.

Various applications on woven composite are presented (SiC-SiC, C-SiC). The simulations are compared with experimental data extracted from literature.

MULTI-SCALE APPROACH

The different scales involves in the description are:

- ✓ Micro-scale: constituents, fiber, matrix, interface,
- ✓ Meso-scale: elementary ply,
- ✓ Macro-scale: composite, structure.

Information obtained from the description of damage evolutions at the micro-scale level are integrated in the construction of the woven composite (or the laminate) modeling. We assumed that in the case of woven composite there is no significant effect of the weaving on the macro-mechanical behaviour (Lorrain, 1994[7]; Dalmaz, 1997[8]). As a consequence, a woven ply could be calculated using two orthogonal layers separated by interface. The interface is then a mechanical surface connecting two adjacent plies. At the micro-scale the thermomechanical behaviour is obtained through a homogenization calculation considering matrix, fibres, and interfaces damageable properties. The prediction of the ply behaviour is obtained using a classical homogenization model (Hashin, 1983[9]; Pideri, 1987[10]). It is based on closed-form analytical solutions, which are available for any thermomechanical loading conditions. Finally, the classical laminate theory is applied to calculate the behaviour of the laminate (Engrand & al., 1996[6]). Obviously the calculation follows the steps:

1. calculation of membrane and curvature deformation from temperature and from plate and shell resultants and moments applied to the laminate,
2. calculation of average plane stress of each ply,
3. calculation of average stress and strain of each constituent (fibre, matrix, interface)
4. calculation of damage variables and failure criteria of each constituent,
5. calculation of ply thermo-elastic properties,
6. calculation of laminate thermo-elastic properties.

The laminate failure occurs by an instability condition on its overall stiffness, which is related to catastrophic damage propagation, or with the failure of the reinforcements (maximum stress or strain criteria).

In CMCs damage occurs at the micro-scale. Thus, in a second step, a suitable model for describing constituent's behaviour based on the anisotropic damage mechanics is used. This allows describing the evolution of damage through damage variables. Damage kinematics and internal variables are deduced together from the theoretical analysis of fiber reinforced matrix composites behaviour (Ladeveze and Ledantec, 1992[3]; Talreja, 1992[11]) and from experimental investigations on progressive degradation (Sorensen & al., 1992[12]; Naslain 1993[13]; Camus & al., 1996[14]; Guillaumat, 1994[15]; Guillaumat and Lamon, 1996[16]).

MICROSCOPIC DESCRIPTION OF THE DEGRADATION MECHANISMS

Assuming experimental results and microscopic observations, the damage mechanisms of CMCs have been well described. Many studies reported the importance of the fiber/matrix interface in controlling the mechanical behaviour of these composites. The mechanical properties can be significantly improved by adjusting the fiber/matrix bonding to deflect the matrix micro-cracks (Naslain, 1993[13]; Leparoux & al., 1997[17]). Under tensile loading, CMCs present a linear elastic response until the initiation and propagation of matrix micro-cracks and the partial re-opening of thermal cracks. These cracks mainly initiate at the singularity of macropores and propagate perpendicularly to the loading direction. In a second

stage, multiplication of matrix micro-cracks and the associated fibre/matrix debonding are propagating until matrix crack saturation (Guillaumat, 1994[15]). Composite with weak interface exhibits a “plateau-like behaviour” (Naslain, 1993[13]). The matrix crack saturation is rapidly achieved (load transfer being poor) and the total failure occurred almost immediately after this saturation point. For composite that present high strain to rupture, after matrix saturation, a significant domain corresponding to a progressive load transfer to the fibres, which then fracture progressively, is observed (El Bouazzaoui & al., 1996[18]). Another net of cracks corresponding to multiple cracking of the bundle could occur (Guillaumat, Lamon, 1996[16]). These composites present a broad non-linear domain and higher stresses without any plateau-like domain.

DAMAGE MODELING

For each damage mechanism one damage parameter should be define. The advantage of this description of damage at the micro-scale is that it allows reproducing all the aspects of the strain-stress curve, like the effect of thermal residual stress. On the other hand, identification of damage parameters is difficult with direct measurement conducted on test results.

Matrix behaviour modeling

The progressive damage resulting from matrix micro-cracking could be defined with three damage variables, two in the direction of the reinforcements, and one to characterize the evolution of the shear modulus. Therefore the elastic energy relative to the matrix is:

$$E_D^m = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\langle \sigma_{11}^m \rangle_+^2}{E_{11}^m (1-d_1^m)} + \frac{\langle \sigma_{11}^m \rangle_-^2}{E_{11}^m} + \frac{\langle \sigma_{22}^m \rangle_+^2}{E_{22}^m (1-d_2^m)} + \frac{\langle \sigma_{22}^m \rangle_-^2}{E_{22}^m} - 2 \frac{\nu_{12}^m}{E_{11}^m} \sigma_{11}^m \sigma_{22}^m + \frac{\sigma_{12}^m{}^2}{G_{12}^m (1-d_{12}^m)} \right]$$

$\langle \rangle_+$ denotes the positive parts of the tensor.

To keep in the standard model framework, d_{12} is completely defined with d_1 and d_2 . Then two damage parameters remain. This expression agrees to the experimental observations. Direction 1 is the reinforcement direction, and 2 is the transverse direction. All the direction of the cracks can be expressed with these two components depending on the orthotropic directions of the ply. We defined:

$$\bar{Y}_i = \text{Sup}_{\tau \leq t} \left(\sqrt{Y_{12}^m + b Y_i^m}, Y_0^m \right)$$

with the conjugate quantities to d_1 and d_2 : $Y_i^m = \left. \frac{\partial E_D^m}{\partial d_i^m} \right|_{\sigma: cst}$ and $Y_0^m = Y_1^m, t = 0$.

This expression is similar to an energy release rate in fracture mechanics. The damage evolution laws are chosen to fit the experimental data. From a physical point of view, we chosed an exponential law that takes into account the load bearing capability of the matrix after the matrix crack saturation (σ_s^m):

$$d_i^m = \begin{cases} d_{\text{lim}} \left(1 - \exp \left(- \frac{Y_i^m - Y_0^m}{Y_c^m} \right) \right) & \text{if } Y_0^m \leq Y_i^m \leq Y_s^m \\ Y_s^m \exp \left(- \frac{Y_i^m - Y_0^m}{Y_c^m} \right) & \\ d_{\text{lim}} \left(1 - \frac{Y_i^m - Y_0^m}{Y_i^m} \right) & \text{if } Y_i^m \geq Y_s^m \end{cases}$$

Y_c^m is the starting point of matrix cracking and Y_s^m is representative of the saturation point of matrix cracking. Therefore, for example:

$$\forall Y_i^m \geq Y_s^m \quad \sigma_{ii}^m = \sqrt{\frac{2E_{ii}}{b} Y_s^m \left(1 - d_{lim} \left(1 - \exp\left(\frac{Y_0^m - Y_s^m}{Y_c^m}\right) \right) \right)} = \sigma_s^m = cst$$

with $b = (\sqrt{E_{11}^m E_{22}^m} / G_{12}^m)$

Y_s^m is linked to Y_c^m and Y_0^m through the damage criterium. Thus, only three parameters remain: Y_c^m , Y_0^m , and d_{lim} which represents the damage induced by matrix microcracking saturation state. They are directly linked to a corresponding stress. To discuss on the value of these damage parameters, the associated stress state will be given (σ_c^m , σ_0^m , and d_{lim}).

Fiber behaviour modeling

The fiber failure could be characterized with one damage parameter, d . A simple failure criteria based on a maximal strain value or stress value is used. This maximum strain is easily extracted from literature (for example, Bunsel & al., 1988[19]). Then the elastic energy is:

$$E_D^f = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\langle \sigma_{11}^f \rangle_+^2}{E_{11}^f (1 - d_1^f)} + \frac{\langle \sigma_{11}^f \rangle_-^2}{E_{11}^f} + \frac{\langle \sigma_{22}^f \rangle_+^2}{E_{22}^f} + \frac{\langle \sigma_{22}^f \rangle_-^2}{E_{22}^f} - 2 \frac{V_{12}^f}{E_{11}^f} \sigma_{11}^f \sigma_{22}^f + \frac{\sigma_{12}^{f2}}{G_{12}^f} \right]$$

The damage law is defined using an exponential law. Y_0^f characterizes of the begining of fiber breakage and Y_c^f depends on the maximum tensile stress supported by fibers:

$$d_1^f = 1 - \exp\left(\frac{Y_1^f - Y_0^f}{Y_c^f}\right)$$

From litterature data, we expressed these parameters (Y_0^f , Y_c^f) with their corresponding stress values (σ_c^f , σ_0^f). σ_0^f represents of the begining of fiber breakage, similar to a statistical parameter, and σ_c^f is the maximum stress before fiber complete failure. This value will be extracted from litterature (Bunsell & al., 1988[19]).

Interfacial behaviour modeling

The mechanical properties of the interface (or interphases) play a significative role on the ply properties. Thus, a first homogenization calculation estimates a homogenized fiber including the interface properties. Then fiber/interface zone is described as a surfacial entity that possesses its own stiffness. Its constitutive law is expressed with a stiffness (k), function of the loads, and that takes values from zero to infinity. Infinity means perfect bonding while zero means failure. Then the damage evolution law is:

$$Y_i(t) = \sup_{\tau \leq t} \left(\sqrt{\frac{(\sigma_{rz}^2(\tau) + \sigma_{r\theta}^2(\tau))_i}{2k_{rz}^0 (1 - d_i'(\tau))^2}} \right)$$

$$d_i' = \begin{cases} \text{Min} \left(\frac{\langle Y^i - Y_0^i \rangle_+}{Y_c^i}, 1 \right) & \langle \sigma_{rr} \rangle_+ \leq \sigma_i^t \\ 1 & \langle \sigma_{rr} \rangle_+ > \sigma_i^t \end{cases} \quad \text{and } d_i' \text{ is constant around the fiber.}$$

Three damage parameters should be estimated, Y_c^m , Y_0^i and σ_i^t .

EXPERIMENTAL - MODEL COMPARISONS

Three composites made at SEP (Société Européenne de Propulsion) are introduced: a SiC-SiC 2D (Nicalon fibre NLM 202), the CERASEP N3-1 (Nicalon fibre NL 207) and a C-SiC 2D (C ex-PAN fibre). Both are processed by Chemical Vapour Infiltration (C.V.I.) of SiC into a fibrous preform with a pyrocarbon interphase previously deposited on fibres. SiC-SiC and C-SiC present opposite thermal expansion mismatch between fibre and matrix. This leads to a thermal-stress free origin of stress-strain axis lying in the compression domain for C-SiC and in the tension domain for SiC-SiC. The mechanical characteristics of the components used in the modeling are extracted from literature. Various SiC-SiC (NLM 202 fibers) have been studied; the SiC-SiC “0.2%” (referring to its ultimate strain under tensile load in orthotropic direction), previously studied by Aubart (1992)[4] and Ladeveze & al. (1994)[5], and the SiC-SiC “0.6%” studied by Guillaumat and Lamon (1996)[16]. The main difference between these two SiC-SiC batches is the quality of fiber/matrix interface. For the “0.6%”, fiber were treated in order to avoid silica around the fiber in the composite. Thus, the load-transfer capability is improved (Naslain, 1993[13]).

SiC CVI matrix properties identification

As we previously mentioned, the direct identification of the damage parameters is almost impossible. As the matter of fact, the constituent’s properties are difficult to obtain from measurement on the composite. Fiber properties and interface properties could be found in the literature, but the mechanical properties of the matrix inside the composite should be identified with at least one calculation. All the examples presented here are composites with C.V.I. SiC matrix. We used the results on SiC-SiC 0.2% (Gasser, 1994[20]) in identification procedures. The SiC C.V.I. matrix properties, including porosity, are identified to reproduce the initial modulus measured with a tensile test in the fiber direction. The constituents properties used in the simulations, including the matrix identified properties, are given in table 1. The given moduli are not affected by temperature during the processing. Besides, the Coefficient of Thermal Expansion should be taken on average between [25-1000°C] to include the thermal residual stresses present from processing into the calculation; It should not be simply estimated with room temperature value (Lebrun, 1996[21]).

	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	ν_{12}	G_{12} (GPa)	α_L ($10^{-6} K^{-1}$)	α_T ($10^{-6} K^{-1}$)	
C-SiC	Nicalon NLM 202 (Lamon & al., 1995[22])	200	200	0.12	80	$4.8 \cdot 10^{-6(1)}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-6(1)}$
	Nicalon NL 207 (Nippon Carbon)	220	220	0.12	$80^{(2)}$	$4.8 \cdot 10^{-6(2)}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-6(2)}$
	Pyrocarbon (Dalmaz, 1997[8])	30	11	0.12	2	$3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$28 \cdot 10^{-6}$
SiC-SiC	SiC CVI matrix	350	310	0.2	146	$4.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$4.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$
	C ex-Pan fiber (Dalmaz, 1997[8])	230	220	0.24	4.8	$1.1 \cdot 10^{6(1)}$	$7 \cdot 10^{6(1)}$

¹ Lebrun, 1996[21]

² estimation

Table 1: Undamaged characteristics of constituents (fibres, matrix and interphase)

Damage parameters identifications

A set of damage parameters is identified using the same test conducted on SiC-SiC 0.2% (Gasser, 1994[20]). From experimental investigation of progressive degradation (Aubart,

1992[4]; Guillaumat, 1994[15]) we know that under tensile loading in the reinforcement direction for the SiC-SiC 0.2 % (Fig.1):

- ✓ The matrix cracking initiates around 85 MPa (end of linearity, $\sigma_o^m=85$ MPa),
- ✓ The matrix crack saturation is rapidly achieved because of a weak bonding between fiber and matrix (Guillaumat, 1994[15]). Then the preexisting cracks begin to open but failure occurs immediately after,
- ✓ On the contrary, for SiC-SiC 0.6%, fibers progressively support the load from the saturation point, up to the failure.

Damage parameters of fibers must be chosen in order to reproduce this observation. The reloading of fibers begins and then fiber breakage occurs. From this information we assumed that fiber damage parameters should be chosen to ensure the beginning of fiber breakage around 185 MPa, with a maximum stress value supported by the fiber around 2.2 ± 0.7 GPa (Bunsell & al., 1988[19]). Interfacial damage parameters and matrix damage parameters are chosen to fit the experimental tensile curve (SiC-SiC 0.2 %, 0° tension, Fig. 1). σ_c^m , which corresponds to the maximum stress value supported by the matrix itself, outside the composite, is 110 MPa. At least, we calculated the interfacial parameters. The corresponding shear maximum value is found around 20 MPa for the SiC-SiC 0.2%, which seems acceptable. The damage parameters used for the modeling are written in the following table 2.

Fig. 1: Identification of intrinsic SiC CVI matrix properties and damage parameters using SiC-SiC 0.2% 0° tensile test.

σ_o^m	σ_c^m	d_{lim}	σ_o^f	σ_c^f	Y_o^i	Y_c^i
85 MPa	110 MPa	0.86	900 MPa	1.6 GPa	$3 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4 \cdot 10^{-2}$
SiC CVI matrix			Nicalon NLM 202		Weak pyrocarbhone interface	

Table 2: Identification of the damage parameters based on the SiC-SiC 0.2% (Gasser, 1994[20])

Experimental - model comparisons

All the studied composites are made with CVI SiC matrix. Thus, if we consider that the identified matrix properties are intrinsic properties, it could be applied to any other composite made with the same matrix. The matrix damage parameters, which are relative to the physical

characteristics of the matrix itself, should be the same. The properties of the C ex-Pan fiber are the one proposed by Dalmaz (1997)[8] and the Nicalon NL 207 are the properties given by the manufacturer (see Table 1). For SiC-SiC 0.6 % and CERASEP N3-1, the interfacial properties were improved, and present a better fiber/matrix load transfer. Thus, the interfacial damage parameters were increased in order to leads to an interfacial shear stress $\tau \approx 200$ MPa.

Fig.2: Identification of interfacial damage parameters using SiC-SiC 0.2% ±45°.

Fig.1 and Fig.2 show the results obtained with the identification procedure of matrix properties and missing damage parameters. These results are satisfactory because the knee point of free thermal residual stress is well reproduced, while the identification was performed to stick to the global curve without considering the unloading-reloading loops. In the case of SiC-SiC, frictions are responsible for the measured inelasticity, and those phenomena have not been considered for the moment. This should be investigated for an extension of the model to cyclic fatigue.

Fig. 3: Experimental results and simulation of a SiC-SiC (0.6%) 0° tension test

A simulation on the SiC-SiC 0.6% was performed, considering the better load transfer between fiber and matrix. The result is given Figures 3 and 4. No other modification on constituents properties or on damage parameters, except the modification of interfacial

parameters ($Y_o^i=3.10^{-1}$, $Y_c^i=5.10^{-1} \Rightarrow \tau \approx 200$ MPa) were done. This simulation proved the intrinsic character of the mechanical properties of the identified SiC CVI matrix.

Fig. 4: Experimental results and simulation of a SiC-SiC (0.6%) +/-45° tension test compared to the SiC-SiC 0.2%, +/-45° tension test.

Using the same set of data, with the manufacturer properties for the Nicalon NL 207 fiber, we simulated the tensile behaviour of the CERASEP N3-1, tested in the reinforcements direction under 20°C and 1200°C. The simulations is given Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Experimental results and simulation of CERASEP N3-1 test performed at Room Temperature and under 1200°C.

For C-SiC, the non-linearity starts almost from the onset of loading. Then, after matrix saturation (≈ 200 MPa), a significant domain corresponding to a progressive load transfer to the fibres, which then fracture progressively, is observed (El Bouazzaoui & al., 1996[18]). Dalmaz (1997)[8] proposed a value of the ultimate stress fiber $\sigma_c^f=3.5$ GPa. Introducing this value and the C ex-Pan properties (table 1), a simulation was performed. This simulation, corresponding to tensile-compressive loading, predicts the point of thermal stress free origin. The simulation is compared to the test results from Camus & al., 1996[14] (Fig. 6). In the case of this composite, the thermal residual stresses are involved in the inelastic strain measured with the periodic unloadings. As the matter of fact, it is well predicted by the model.

Fig. 6: Experimental results and simulation of a C-SiC 0° tension-compression test

CONCLUSIONS

A damage micro-macro model, including information on the micro-mechanical damage mechanisms, has been investigated. The damage evolution laws, written at the micro-scale, take into account the main damage phenomena observed for this kind of composite. Homogenization procedures have been written to calculate the damage ply behaviour and then the laminate behaviour. This model is able to perform simulations on various CMC, even woven composite, under complex thermomechanical loading up to the final failure. Such a simulation needs knowledge of the constituent's thermomechanical properties. Thus, we performed an identification of the matrix SiC CVI properties, using the test results on the SiC-SiC 0.2% (Gasser, 1994[20]). These identified properties were input in the model to perform simulation on other composite made with the same matrix (SiC-SiC 0.6%, CERASEP N3-1 and C-SiC). Interfacial properties and fiber properties are extracted from literature (table 1). The predictions obtained for these composites proved the intrinsic character of the matrix properties previously identified. It allows to simulate with success the behaviour of various composites with SiC CVI matrix and with various fibres (or bundle) and various interfaces. Moreover, the simulations performed are satisfactory and validated the model. Thermal residual stress effect is well predicted for SiC-SiC and C-SiC composite. These thermal residual stresses could be responsible for various effects like inelastic strain for IC-SiC composite and can not be avoided for the prediction of structure behaviour.

This model can be introduced in a structural analysis code to predict the state of a structure under complex loading before a macrocrack appears.

As the damage is introduced at the micro-scale, this model is able to predict the evolution of damage of each constituent and then give the history of the composite damage under the applied load. In addition to the prediction of the stress-strain curve this could be useful for new composite or complex structure survey.

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